

Kinetic behavior of cis -[Pt(*cis*-dach)(H₂O)₂]²⁺ (where 'dach' is 1,2-diaminocyclohexane) towards some essential amino acids

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Abstract : We report the kinetic study of a cationic platinum(II) complex. The reactivity of cis -[Pt(*cis*-dach)(H₂O)₂]²⁺ (where 'dach' is 1,2-diaminocyclohexane) was investigated by studying the interaction with some bio-relevant amino acids namely, aspartic acid (L₁H), glutamine (L₂H) and alanine (L₃H) in aqueous medium. The kinetic study has been substantiated by product isolation, UV, IR and ESI-MS spectroscopic analysis and rate parameters have been evaluated under different reaction conditions.

Keywords : Kinetic, platinum(II), diaminocyclohexane, amino acids.

Introduction

Malignant disease is a major cause of mortality all over the world. The era of chemotherapy commenced in the late 1940s and 1950s with the clinical introduction of the classical alkylating agents (e.g. nitrogen mustard, cyclophosphamide, and melphalan), anti metabolites (e.g. methotrexate and 5-fluorouracil) with a marked improvement particularly in the treatment of lymphomas and leukemias. Plant alkaloids (e.g. vinca alkaloids and taxoids) and hormonal agents (e.g. tamoxifen) are the more recent clinically effective antitumor cytotoxic drugs¹.

The classical coordination complex *cis*-diammine-dichloroplatinum(II) or *cis*-DDP or cisplatin, has been the subject of much recent attention because of its advantageous effects in the treatment of cancer^{2,3}. Introduction of *cis*-DDP inspired great efforts to design similarly effective platinum agents that conquer the three main limitations of cisplatin i.e. toxicity, tumor resistance and poor oral bioavailability. To the structural chemist, it is most captivating that only the *cis*-isomer displays anticancer activity. Among the Pt derivatives, the complexes containing the 1,2-diaminocyclohexane (DACH) ligand in-veterate anticancer activity in cell lines with acquired *cis*-DDP resistance^{4,5}. The chirality at the carrier 1,2-diaminocyclohexane ligand can influence some impera-

tive structural properties of the interstrand cross-links of cisplatin analogues^{6,7}.

Nuclear DNA has been recognized as the principal target of cisplatin, which covalently binds to adjoining guanine bases resulting in a cascade of events that ultimately lead to cell death. We preferred the above mentioned amino acids because platinum complexes can also interact with other molecules in a cellular environment, like peptide structures or RNA's. Assessment of the modes of action of metal-based antitumor drugs therefore requires the study of their interactions with a range of probable biological targets including amino acids, hormones, peptides and proteins. The study of model species such as simple amino acids can give a hand in the construal of more composite systems. In continuation of our earlier work⁸, in this paper, we represent the kinetic and mechanistic aspects of the interaction of cis -[Pt(*cis*-dach)(OH₂)₂]²⁺ with the three amino acids.

Results and discussion

Spectroscopic analysis :

The electronic spectra of the reactant complex (1) and product complexes are shown in Fig. 1. From the absorption spectra it is very clear that those product complexes (for L₁H, L₂H and L₃H) exhibit maximum ab-

Fig. 1. Absorbance differences between complex (1), aspartic acid (L_1H) substituted product (2), glutamine (L_2H) substituted product (3) and alanine (L_3H) substituted product (4), [complex 1] = 2×10^{-4} mol dm^{-3} , [amino acids] = 4×10^{-3} mol dm^{-3} , pH = 4.0 and cell used = 1 cm quartz.

Fig. S₁. A typical kinetic plot of $\ln(A_{\infty} - A_t)$ versus time. [Complex (1)] = 2.0×10^{-4} mol dm^{-3} ; [L_1H] = 3×10^{-3} mol dm^{-3} ; Temperature = 55 °C.

sorption at 221, 224 and 212 nm respectively.

The IR spectrum of the yellow product, isolated from the (1 : 1) mixture of the substrate complex (1) and amino acid (L_1H), in the KBr disc shows strong bands at 3416 and 627 cm^{-1} together with prominent bands at 3150–

2900 cm^{-1} and 466 cm^{-1} . The presence of strong stretching band at 3416 cm^{-1} indicates that the product is hydrated. The asymmetric COO^- stretching frequency (ν_{asym}) of the amino acids occurs at 1580–1660 cm^{-1} , when the group is coordinated to metals, whereas a non-coordinated COO^- group has the $\nu_{asym}(COO^-)$ stretching at

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Fig. S2. A typical kinetic plot of $\ln \Delta$ versus time. $[\text{Complex (1)}] = 2 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$; $[\text{L}_1\text{H}] = 3 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$; Temperature = 55 °C.

lower frequency⁹. The band at 1686, 1612 cm^{-1} is therefore due to the ν_{asym} (COOH) of the metal bonded carboxyl group. The broad band at 3150–2900 cm^{-1} may be due to overlapping of the ν_{asym} and ν_{sym} motion -NH_2 bending motion coordinated to platinum. The presence of

a band at 466 cm^{-1} indicates the presence of (Pt-N) bond¹⁰. From the individual assignments of different bands it can be presumed that the final product is a (O, N) coordinated chelate and amino acids behaves like a bidentate ligand in the experimental pH (Figs. 2 and S₃).

Fig. 2. IR spectrum of the (L_1H) substituted product.

Fig. S₃. IR spectrum of the (L₃H) substituted product.

ESI-MS of the resulting solutions, obtained from the (1 : 1) mixture of the substrate complex (**1**) and three amino acids, are shown in Figs. 3, S₄ and S₅. It is clear from this spectrum that the ion at m/z 441.04, 454.15 and 397.05 (major peak) for (L₁H, L₂H and L₃H) has become the precursor ion species in the mixture solution and this is cautiously attributed to [amino acid + Pt + (*cis*-dach)] the relative abundance of isotope peaks match the predictable values. The precursor ions are made known schematically in Fig. 4.

We proposed that Pt^{II} is likely to be coordinated to both COO⁻ and NH₂ considering the strong coordination ability of these functional groups¹¹⁻¹³. Thus the structure proposed here for product ion species, deduced from ESI-MS and IR are generally consistent with those derived from other experimental methods.

Kinetic studies :

The pK_a values of the amino acids L₁H, L₂H and L₃H are 2.09 α(-COOH), 9.82 (-COOH), 3.86 α(NH₃⁺); 2.17 α(-COOH), 9.13 α(NH₃⁺) and 2.34 α(-COOH),

9.69 α(NH₃⁺)¹⁴, respectively, at 25 °C. From the pK_a values of the ligands it can be concluded that at pH 4.0, ligands L₁H, L₂H and L₃H remain in the Zwitterionic form, which take part in the reaction. The pK₁ and pK₂ values for *cis*-[Pt(*cis*-dach)(H₂O)₂]²⁺ has been evaluated by Irving-Rossotti method¹⁵ and found to be 6.25 and 7.80 respectively, and hence it can be assumed that at pH 4.0 the reactant complex exists as diaqua ion. The reaction between complex (**1**) and amino acids involve a two step consecutive route; we put forward that in the first step one aqua ligand is replaced from *cis*-[Pt(*cis*-dach)(OH₂)₂]²⁺ by the LH. The second step is slower, where the remaining aqua ligand is substituted with chelate ring closure. The rate constant for such a process can be evaluated by assuming the following scheme :

where A is the diaqua species (**1**), B is the single substituted intermediate and C is the final product (**2**), [Pt(*cis*-dach)(L)]⁺. Formation of C from B is predominant after some time has elapsed.

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Fig. 3. ESI-mass spectra of the (L_1H) substituted product.

Fig. S₄. ESI-mass spectra of the (L_2H) substituted product.

Fig. S₅. ESI-mass spectra of the (L₃H) substituted product.

Fig. 4. Plausible structure of the precursor ion peaks from the ESI-mass spectra.

Calculation of k_1 :

The rate constants ($k_{1(\text{obs})}$) for the $A \rightarrow B$ step were evaluated by the method of Weyh and Hamm¹⁶ using the usual consecutive rate law (we did not use graphing software for calculation of k_1 , as we have noticed that where the plots shows initial curvature, the Weyh and Hamm method gives good results. In other places, we used Origin software for calculations).

$$(A_\infty - A_t) = a_1 \exp(-k_{1(\text{obs})}t) + a_2 \exp(-k_{2(\text{obs})}t) \quad (1)$$

where a_1 and a_2 are constants that depend upon the rate constant and extinction coefficient. Values of $(A_\infty - A_t) - a_2 \exp(-k_{2(\text{obs})}t)$ were obtained from X to Y plots at different time, so that

$$\Delta = a_1 \exp(-k_{1(\text{obs})}t)$$

or

$$\ln \Delta = \text{constant} - k_{1(\text{obs})}t \quad (2)$$

where Δ is the difference of $\ln(A_\infty - A_t)$ values between the observed and extrapolated part of the linear portion of $\ln(A_\infty - A_t)$ versus t curve at any t . The value of $k_{1(\text{obs})}$ was derived from the slope of $\ln \Delta$ versus t for small t (Fig. S₂). A similar procedure was applied for each ligand concentration in the range of 0.002–0.004 mol dm⁻³ at constant complex (1) concentration of 0.0002 mol dm⁻³ at pH 4.0 and at 35, 40, 45, 50 and 55 °C, respectively. The $k_{1(\text{obs})}$ values thus obtained are linearly dependent on the studied concentration range. The $k_{1(\text{obs})}$ values for different ligand concentrations at different temperatures are given in Table 1.

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Fig. 5. Plot of $k_{1(\text{obs})}$ (s^{-1}) versus $[\text{L}_1\text{H}]$ at different temperatures. A = 35, B = 40, C = 45, D = 50 and E = 55 °C.

The following mechanism is proposed :

where LH is the Zwitterionic form of amino acids. Based on the above scheme, a rate expression eq. (4) can be derived for the A $\rightarrow$ B step :

$$dB/dt = k_1[\text{Pt}(\text{dach})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2^{2+}]_{\text{total}} [\text{LH}] \quad (3)$$

where $[\text{Pt}(\text{dach})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2^{2+}]_{\text{total}}$ is the concentration of the unreacted complex. Hence, we can write

$$k_{1(\text{obs})} = k_1[\text{LH}] \quad (4)$$

where k_1 is the second-order rate constant for the first aqua ligand substitution. A plot of $k_{1(\text{obs})}$ (s^{-1}) versus $[\text{LH}]$ should be linear, passing through the origin. This was found to be so at all temperatures studied (Figs. 5, S₆ and S₇). The second-order rate constants (k_1) calculated from the slope of the plot of $k_{1(\text{obs})}$ (s^{-1}) versus $[\text{LH}]$ (mol dm^{-3}) at different temperatures are given in Table 2.

Table 1. $10^3 k_{1(\text{obs})}$ (s^{-1}) values for different concentrations of (LH) at different temperatures. $[\text{Complex (1)}] = 2 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, pH = 4.0, $\mu = 0.1 \text{ mol dm}^{-3} \text{ NaClO}_4$

Ligand	Temp. (± 0.1 °C)	$10^3 [\text{L}]$ (mol dm^{-3})				
		2.00	2.50	3.00	3.50	4.00
L ₁ H	35	0.54	0.68	0.81	0.95	1.07
	40	0.66	0.81	0.99	1.13	1.30
	45	0.84	1.10	1.26	1.48	1.68
	50	1.11	1.41	1.69	1.97	2.24
	55	1.46	1.83	2.23	2.58	2.94
L ₂ H	35	0.47	0.59	0.70	0.83	0.95
	40	0.57	0.71	0.86	1.01	1.15
	45	0.73	0.90	1.08	1.27	1.45
	50	0.92	1.16	1.39	1.63	1.85
	55	1.23	1.56	1.85	2.18	2.47
L ₃ H	35	0.20	0.25	0.29	0.34	0.41
	40	0.25	0.31	0.36	0.43	0.52
	45	0.32	0.40	0.47	0.56	0.63
	50	0.41	0.51	0.62	0.70	0.80
	55	0.50	0.67	0.76	0.88	1.02

Calculation of k_2 :

The B $\rightarrow$ C step is assigned to ring closure in which the NH_2 group of the amino acids binds the metal centre through N. Due to steric hindrance; this chelation step is slow and independent of ligand concentration. At each

Fig. S₆. Plot of $k_{1(\text{obs})}$ (s^{-1}) versus $[\text{L}_2\text{H}]$ at different temperatures. A = 35, B = 40, C = 45, D = 50 and E = 55 °C.

Fig. S₇. Plot of $k_{1(\text{obs})}$ (s^{-1}) versus $[\text{L}_3\text{H}]$ at different temperatures. A = 35, B = 40, C = 45, D = 50 and E = 55 °C.

temperature, the k_2 values were calculated from the limiting linear portion (when t is large) of the $\ln(A_\infty - A_t)$ versus t curves and are collected in Table 2. Unlike k_1 , k_2 was found to be independent of ligand concentration at each of the temperatures studied.

Effects of pH and temperature on the reaction rate :

Effects of pH on reaction rate :

The reaction was studied at four different pH (2.8,

3.4, 4.0 and 4.6) values. The $k_{(\text{obs})}$ values increased with increase in pH; at fixed concentration of (2×10^{-4} mol dm^{-3} of complex (1), 3×10^{-3} mol dm^{-3} aspartic acid) and 0.1 mol dm^{-3} ionic strength. The increase in rate may be explained based on the acid dissociation equilibria of the amino acids and the complex. In the studied pH range, the complex starts to switch into hydroxo-aqua species from diaqua species. The enhancement in rate there-

Table 2. k_1 and k_2 values for the substitution reaction

Ligand	Temp. (°C)	$10^2 k_1$ (mol ⁻¹ dm ³ s ⁻¹)	$10^5 k_2$ (s ⁻¹)
L ₁ H	35	2.69	1.48
	40	3.24	1.98
	45	4.21	2.61
	50	5.62	3.44
	55	7.37	4.43
L ₂ H	35	2.72	2.01
	40	2.88	2.56
	45	3.62	3.27
	50	4.64	4.10
	55	6.19	5.31
L ₃ H	35	1.06	1.65
	40	1.26	2.15
	45	1.58	2.77
	50	2.01	3.65
	55	2.54	4.85

fore explained by the deprotonation and increased donor ability of the amino acid and reactant complex. The characteristic pH dependence for the substitution reaction can be theoretically explained by considering the following derived rate expression :

$$k_{\text{obs}} = k_a K_a [L]_t / K_a + [H^+]$$

where, k_a , K_a and $[L]_t$ are the rate constant, acid dissociation constant of the amino acid carboxylate group and total amino acid concentration, respectively. In subsequent kinetic runs, the substitution reactions were followed at a constant pH of 4.0 to avoid complications from an additional parameter of $[H^+]$ to the rate equation.

Effects of temperature on reaction rate :

These reactions were monitored at five different temperatures for diverse ligand concentrations and the anation rate constants for both A → B (k_1) and B → C (k_2) steps

are arranged in Table 2. The activation parameters calculated from Eyring plots are tabulated in Table 3 and are compared with those for parallel systems related to the substitution in square planar platinum(II) complexes.

Mechanism and conclusion :

In summary, from the pKa values it is clear that all three amino acids exist as Zwitterion at pH 4.0. It appears that a mechanism based on the stabilization of the five member chelate ring formation is the most reasonable, our results strongly support this mechanism both logically and experimentally. Our observations have shown the present investigation of aqua ligands substitution in [Pt(*cis*-dach)(H₂O)₂]²⁺, by three different amino acids, follows an associative mode of activation in the transition state. The succeeding step is the chelate ring closure step, which is slower than the first step and independent of ligand concentration. The rate constant ' k_1 ' for the ligands aspartic acid (L₁H), glutamine (L₂H) and alanine (L₃H), all having (O, N) donor set and can be rearranged as :

Aspartic acid (L₁H) > Glutamine (L₂H) > Alanine (L₃H)

The first step is related with the deprotonation of -COOH group. So decrease in rate from aspartic acid to alanine is associated with the pKa values of the ligands.

The chelation reaction also shows different rates for different amino acids. The rate constant for this reaction k_2 has been found to be in the order :

Glutamine (L₂H) > Alanine (L₃H) > Aspartic acid (L₁H)

Chelation step is accompanied by deprotonation of the α -NH₃⁺ of the amino acids. So rate constant values for the second step are in accordance with pKa of α -NH₃⁺ group. The $\Delta H_1^\ddagger$ and $\Delta H_2^\ddagger$ values and negative $\Delta S_1^\ddagger$ and $\Delta S_2^\ddagger$ values entail a good extent of ligand participation in the transition state.

Table 3. Activation parameters for complex (I) by L₁H, L₂H and L₃H in aqueous medium, at pH 4.0

Ligands	$\Delta H_1^\ddagger$ (kJ mol ⁻¹)	$\Delta S_1^\ddagger$ (JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹)	$\Delta H_2^\ddagger$ (kJ mol ⁻¹)	$\Delta S_2^\ddagger$ (JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹)	Ref.
L ₁ H	40.4 ± 2.2	-125 ± 7	50.1 ± 2.5	-173 ± 8	This work
L ₂ H	41.3 ± 2.0	-123 ± 6	46.4 ± 5.4	-184 ± 17	This work
L ₃ H	45.6 ± 2.9	-118.3 ± 9	49.6 ± 4.1	-175 ± 11	This work

Experimental

Materials :

K_2PtCl_4 , *cis*-1,2-diaminocyclohexane (*cis*-DACH) were obtained from Sigma and amino acids were obtained from SRL. Unless stated, all other reagents used in this research were obtained from commercial sources and used without purification. Solution of the Pt complex and other reagents used for this study were prepared freshly in doubly-distilled water before use.

Instrumentation :

The pH measurements were carried out with the help of a Sartorius Digital pH meter (model PB11) with an accuracy of ± 0.01 units. Electronic spectra were measured on a Shimadzu 2450 spectrophotometer. Infrared (IR) spectroscopy on KBr pellets was performed on a Perkin-Elmer FT-IR model RX1 infrared spectrophotometer

from 4000 to 400 cm^{-1} . ESI-MS were recorded using a micromass Q-ToF microTM mass spectrometer in +ve ion mode. Kinetic measurements were monitored on a Shimadzu spectrophotometer (UV-2450) equipped with a Shimadzu TCC 240A cell temperature controller (accuracy $\pm 0.1\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$).

Methods :

The reactant complex *cis*- $[\text{Pt}(\text{cis-dach})(\text{OH}_2)_2](\text{ClO}_4)_2$ (**1**) (*dach* = 1,2-diaminocyclohexane) was prepared from K_2PtCl_4 according to the reported method⁸. The above stated reactant complex (**1**) was then characterized spectrophotometrically. The products of the reaction between complex (**1**) and amino acids were separately prepared by mixing the reactants at pH 4.0 in different molar ratios, namely 1 : 1, 1 : 2, 1 : 3, 1 : 4 and 1 : 5, and thermostating the mixtures at $60\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for 48 h. The absorption spectra of

Fig. 6. A typical Job's plot for the reaction between complex (1) and (L₁H) at pH = 4.0 and ionic strength = 0.1 mol dm⁻³ NaClO₄.

the resulting solutions were recorded and each set were found to exhibit almost identical absorbance at the characteristic wavelengths irrespective of their different molar ratios. The difference in spectra between the product complexes and the substrate complex is shown in Fig. 1. The pH of the solutions was adjusted by adding NaOH/HClO₄ at pH 4.0 so that reactant complex (1) exists as diaqua species in the reaction mixture.

The 1 : 1 metal-ligand composition of the product for all in solution was determined by Job's method of continuous variation (Fig. 6).

$Cis\text{-[Pt}(cis\text{-dach})(\text{OH}_2)]^{2+}$ (1) and all three amino acids were separately mixed in 1 : 1 ratio at the already mentioned pH and three different products were isolated. These products were finally characterized by IR and Mass spectroscopy.

In the kinetic measurements the absorbance at corresponding wavelength was monitored to follow the progress of the reaction. The absorption due to ligand was subtracted by using 1 : 1 (molar ratio) ligand : water mixture in the reference cell. Conventional mixing technique was followed, and pseudo-first order conditions with respect to metal concentration were maintained throughout the course of the reaction. Plots of $\ln(A_\infty - A_t)$ (where A_t and A_∞ are absorbance at time t and at infinite time or after

completion of the reaction) against time (t) (Fig. S₁) were found to be nonlinear, being curved at the initial stage and subsequently of constant slope, indicating that the reaction proceeds via two consecutive steps. From the limiting linear portion of the curve, values of $k_{2(\text{obs})}$ were obtained. The $k_{1(\text{obs})}$ values were obtained from plots of $\ln \Delta$ versus time, where time is small (Fig. S₂). Origin software was used for computational analysis. Rate data, represented as an average of duplicate runs, were reproducible to within $\pm 4\%$.

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